

In-depth logical analysis of special relativity

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we deeply analysis Einstein's two famous papers that regard special relativity in every aspect. We discuss in every detail with respect to inconsistency of the simultaneity, relativity of length and time, derivations and interpretations of Lorentz transformation. We identified that the special relativity is only a postulate. This postulate is for eliminating the conflict between the observation ($c' = c - v$) as per Galilean transformation (assuming it is correct) and the principle of relativity ($c' = c$). The time dilation is based on a thought experiment of inconsistency of simultaneity, and length contraction is based on time dilation. We have concluded in previous paper that Galilean transformation is incorrect, and have identified in this paper that inconsistency of simultaneity does not exists, therefore, the reason for the postulate of special relativity is not convincing.

This paper derived Logical transformation to replace Lorentz transformation. We identified the derivations and interpretations of Lorentz transformation do not satisfy logical self-consistent. We concluded when we observe particle motions in a moving frame, the moving frame's math time is not equal to its physical time.

KEYWORD

special relativity; logical transformation; Lorentz transformation; Lorentz factor; covariance; Galilean transformation; relativistic mechanics; space time; fundamental physics theory; Maxwell; Einstein; observation; logical; derivation; covariant.

What is the special relativity? There are three explanations.

The first explanation states that due to the relativity of time, light speed in a moving frame is c , i.e. $c' = c$. We have concluded in paper [2] that $c' = c$ is correct but it is regardless of relativity of time.

The second explanation states that the special relativity is correct because relativistic mechanics is applied to high-energy physics widely. Yes, most one-dimensional equations of relativistic mechanics are correct but the derivations of one-dimensional relativistic mechanics are not required Lorentz factor. We have derived three-dimensional Logical transformation to replace one-dimensional Lorentz transformation in paper [3], and to replace the incorrect equations of three-dimensional of relativistic mechanics.

The third explanation states that time and length measurements are relativity between two reference frames, which are in relative motion. Also, Einstein said "General laws of nature are covariant with respect to Lorentz transformations" (Paper [5], Pg 41). These issues are very complicated. We are going to discuss them in detail in this paper. We analyze Einstein's two original papers to discuss the special relativity derivations and interpretations. Einstein's two papers are "On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies" paper [4], 1905, and "Relativity: The Special and General Theory" paper [5], 1916. We have concluded in paper [1] that Galilean transformation is not correct. Following lists the partial conclusions we obtained in previous three papers.

- Einstein's formulas $u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2)$, $m = \gamma(u)m_0$, $E = mc^2$ are correct [3]. Einstein's postulates of invariance of light speed and principle of relativity are correct [2].
- According to the principle of invariance of light speed, we have derived **one-dimensional Logical transformation** [3]:

$$x' = x - vt \quad x'\text{-axis and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \quad (1)$$

$$t'^* = t - vx/c^2 \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v, v < c \quad (2)$$

$$u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v \quad (3)$$

$$u' = (u + v)/(1 + vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is opposite to } v \quad (4)$$

$$y' = y \quad z' = z \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is along } y\text{-axis or } z\text{-axis} \quad (5)$$

$$t'^* = t \quad \text{when particle moving along } y\text{-axis or } z\text{-axis} \quad (6)$$

$$u' = u \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is along } y\text{-axis or } z\text{-axis} \quad (7)$$

Where t'^* is mathematical time. $t'^* = t$, when particle moving along y -axis or z -axis due to no relative motion along y -axis or z -axis directions between two reference frames.

- According to three-dimensional setup of two reference frames as shown in Fig. 1, we have derived

three-dimensional Logical transformation [3]:

$$\gamma'_{BC} = \gamma_{AC} - vt \quad (8)$$

$$t'^* = t - v\gamma_{AC}/c^2 \quad (9)$$

$$u' = (u - v)/(1 - uv/c^2) \quad (10)$$

Since Lorentz transformation and Galilean transformation are based on one-dimensional setup as shown in Fig. 4, they

are not suitable for particle motions in three-dimensional space. Eq. (8), (9) and (10) are the solution.

From Eqs.(8), (9) and (10), we can obtain $m = \gamma(u)m_0$, $E = mc^2$, and we can correct the three-dimensional equations of relativistic mechanics. Please read paper [3] for details.

- Galilean speed transformation:

$$u' = u - v \quad \text{or} \quad u = u' + v \quad (11)$$

Fig. 1

$$c' = c - v \quad \text{for photon motion, the directions of } v \text{ and } c \text{ are the same.} \quad (12)$$

$$c' = c + v \quad \text{for photon motion, the directions of } v \text{ and } c \text{ are opposite.} \quad (13)$$

- Invariance of light speed:

$$c' = c \quad \text{Regardless of the relative motion between two reference frames} \quad (14)$$

We have proved in paper [2] that Eq. (14) is correct regardless of time dilation.

For better understanding, first we introduce Einstein's logical thinking in paper [4].

- 1) According to Galilean transformation, light speed in moving frame is $c' = c - v$ (Pg 20). "But this result comes into conflict with the principle of relativity". According the principle of relativity, it should be $c' = c$. "At this juncture the theory of relativity entered the arena. As a result of an analysis of the physical conceptions of time and space, it became evident that in really there is not the least incompatibility between the principle of relativity and the law of propagation of light" (Pg 20). This means if we do not change physical conceptions of time and space, the result of light speed in moving frame is $c' = c - v$.
- 2) Einstein proposed Lorentz transformation and got $x' = c t'$, i.e. $c' = c$ (Pg 32, 33). Please note that the Lorentz factor $1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ is deleted when he got $x' = c t'$ (Pg 33). And then, Einstein pointed out that Eq. (11) is incorrect, and Eq. (17) is correct (Pg 37, 38).
- 3) From Eq. (17), Einstein obtained his famous equations of relativistic mechanics (Pg 42-45). Please note that the symbol v should be replaced by u . v is the speed of moving frame while u is a particle speed in stationary frame. Please note that Eq. (17) is the result of a transformation, not observation.
- 4) Einstein use Lorentz factor $1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ to explain the observation results of time dilation in a moving frame and length contraction in a moving frame (Pg 34-36). Please note that they are observation results, not measurement results.

The questions are: Why do we have to hypothesize time dilation to suit $c' = c - v$? Why not use Eq.(3) instead of Eq. (11) to make observations (it will be $c' = c$)? Why is Lorentz factor deleted to get $c' = c$? Why does not contain Lorentz factor or v in Einstein's famous equations?

1. Derivation of a correct transformation; physical concepts of time and distance

Any postulate must be logical self-consistent, because it is the necessary condition to understand the postulate. All deviations of equations must be based on correct physics concepts, math logics and common sense. If physics concepts of time and space must be changed, all physical laws must be changed accordingly, not just for a special field. Imaginative thought experiment must satisfy causal logic and mathematical logic.

1. Here, we provide a simple derivation for Eq.(1), (2), (3),(4). For complete derivation, please read paper [3]. Referring in Fig.2, A photon motion can be measured by observer- A in frame S . The distance is $x = AC$; time is t ; speed is c . All these physical quantities are regardless of the motion of $A'B'$ -rod. $A'B'$ -rod motion can also be measured by observer- A in frame S . The distance is $x_0 = AA' = vt$; time is t ; speed is v . All these physical quantities are also regardless of the motion of the photon.

Now, observer- A makes a logical thinking. What observer- A' would see? Observer- A' would see that $A'B'$ -rod is stationary and AB -rod is moving to left side. The moving distance of the photon is $x' = A'C$; time is t' ; speed is c' . The moving distance of AB -rod is $x'_0 = A'A$; time would be t' ; speed would be v' . And $v' = -v$; $c' = c$. Also, $t' = t$, because frames S' and S are both under same physics building (same standard atomic clocks). t and t' are called physical time.

Form Fig. 2, and viewing from frame S, we obtain Eq. (1), $x' = x - vt$. The physical meaning of this equation is that the photon travel distance in $S'(x', y', z')$ (represents math space) is less than the photon travel distance in $S(x, y, z)$ (represents physical space).

Where is the moving start point of the photon? From Fig. 2, we can see there are different judgments between observer-A and observer- A'. Form the viewpoint of observer-A, it must be $t^* \neq t$, since $x' \neq x$ and $c' = c$. This means there is a discrepancy of math time (t^*) and physical time (t') in frame S', i.e. $t^* \neq t'$ ($t' = t$). Referring to Fig. 2, this discrepancy is:

$$t - t^* = t_0^* = x'_0/c' = vt/c' = vx/c'c = vx/c^2$$

Thus, we obtain Eq.(2), $t^* = t - vx/c^2$. From Eq.(1) and (2), we obtain Eq.(3):

$$u' = dx'/dt^* = \frac{dx'/dt}{dt'/dt} = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2)$$

Based on above equation or Eq. (17), we can obtain Einstein's formulas $m = \gamma(u)m_0$, $E = mc^2$ [3]. Above equation can also be obtained from Lorentz transformation, Eq.(34) and (35). However, the Lorentz factor of Eq.(34), (35) is deleted to obtain above equation:

$$u' = \frac{dx'}{dt'} = \frac{dx'/dt}{dt'/dt} = \frac{1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} d(x-vt)/dt}{1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} d(t-vx/c^2)/dt} = \frac{d(x-vt)/dt}{d(x-vx/c^2)/dt} = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2)$$

Without Lorentz factor of Lorentz transformation is actually one-dimensional Logical transformation, i.e. Eq.(1) and (2). However, for particles moving in three-dimensional space, we must use **three-dimensional Logical transformation**, i.e. Eq.(8), (9) and (10). Please read paper [3].

Our goal is to obtain equation (3) for any particle motion, not a thought experiment of photon motion. Thus, we conclude that math time t^* (rather than physical time t') must be used for obtaining particle speed relationship between frame S' and S. Galilean speed transformation, Eq.(11), (12) and (13) are obtained from a postulate $t^* = t$, $t^* = t'$, so they are incorrect. In addition, two point distance in physical space is invariant as per mathematical definition, so $x'_0 = x_0$.

On the other hand, observer- A' would see:

$$x = x' + vt' \quad x'-axis \text{ and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \tag{15}$$

$$t^* = t' + vx'/c^2 \quad u' \text{ direction is the same as } x'-axis, v \text{ direction is opposite to } u' \tag{16}$$

$$u = (u' + v)/(1 + vu'/c^2) \quad u' \text{ direction is the same as } x'-axis \tag{17}$$

$$u = (u' - v)/(1 - vu'/c^2) \quad u' \text{ direction is opposite to } x'-axis \tag{18}$$

- What is motion? What is stationary? Please see Fig. 3. There are relative motions between A and B, A and C. But no one can tell what is the motion speed of A, B and C until we attach a stationary reference frame S on one of objects. If we attach a stationary reference frame S on object A, the object A is stationary (at rest), and the object B is in motion with speed u, object C is in motion with speed v. If we attach a frame S' on object C, the speed of frame S' is v. Thus, we can obtain the speed of object B in frame S' by using a transformation equation, i.e. we can obtain the relative speed between objects B and C. We can

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

verify whether the transformation equation is correct by measuring the speed (u') of object B in frame S' .

The x and t transformations are for deriving speed transformation. No one can tell any time relationship between A, B and C from Fig. 3 until we define what is the time. If we use physical time for reference frame S , we can obtain physical laws by measuring the motions of objects B and C in reference frame S . If we use mathematical time for frame S' , we can obtain the correct speed relationship of objects B between frames S and S' .

We may assume that nature time exists, but we are not able to measure nature time. Object A, B, C can be big or small, but there are all in equal status, i.e. the earth frame and a moving train frame are in equal status. The earth or the sun is not an absolute stationary frame.

- Fig. 4 is two frames setup for deriving Lorentz transformation, Galilean transformation and one-dimensional Logical transformation. We can see there is no relative motion between y and y' or z and z' , and the motion direction of particle Q is parallel to x -axis, so velocity components of particle Q in y and z directions are zero. Therefore, we can't imagine any time dilation in directions of y and z .

As shown in Fig.4, frame $S'(x', t', u')$ and frame $S(x, t, u)$ are in relative uniform motion. The relative speed is v . The x' -axis and x -axis overlap each other. Particle Q is moving in x -axis positive direction. As we discuss above, we use symbol t'^* to represent math time in frame S' for obtaining the speed relationship of particle Q between frames S and S' . Since speed is a function of time and distance, we call $t'^* = f(t, x, v)$ and $x' = f(t, x, v)$ basic transformations. See Eq.(1), (2), (8), (9).

Referring to Fig. 4, observers S' and S always have opposite opinion for who is in motion? Observe S defines himself is stationary and frame S' is moving to right side; observe S' also defines himself is stationary and frame S is moving to left side.

In this paper, we divide time into nature time, physical time and math time. We will discuss nature time in Section 4.2. Physical time t or t' is independent variable, which is defined by physics. The measurement of physical time is by a standard clock, which is located at London Greenwich. We use cesium atomic clocks to represent the standard clock for different locations. Physical time is never changed by any observation since it is an independent variable. The interval and rate of time t' in frame S' are always equal to the interval and rate of time t in frame S , i.e. $t' = t$, since all physical laws are the same in frames S and S' .

Mathematical time (t'^*) is a dependent variable, which is defined by an equation (i.e. by observer S), $t'^* = f(t, x, v)$. There is no math time (t'^*) unless we study a particle motion in both frames S and S' . When we transform a particle motion from frame S to S' , we must use math time (t'^*); otherwise we cannot obtain the correct result.

The distance between two points in physical space is the same regardless of reference frames, since physical laws are the same in frames S and S' . Math distance (x'^*) is equal to physical distance (x'). We only have ONE PHYSICAL SPACE. The frame (x, y, z) which we select as the reference frame represents the physical space (stationary), and all other frames (x', y', z') represent math spaces (moving).

Fig. 4

2. Preparation for deriving Lorentz transformation

In Einstein's Paper-4 [4], Pg.3-5, Einstein gave the definition of simultaneity, described relativity of lengths and times, which are related to light propagation. In Einstein's Paper-5 [5], Pg.30, Einstein postulated that time-interval and space-interval are related to the motion of reference frame, and described the famous sample of the simultaneity train. Let us take a deep look for these fantastic concepts.

2.1 The statement of the inconsistency of simultaneity

In Einstein's Paper-5 [5], Pg.25-27, Einstein demonstrated a famous example of simultaneity train. Einstein discovered inconsistency of simultaneity between frames S and S' . See Fig.5. An open-compartments train moves on the railway at speed v . When M' and M were vertically aligned, two light signals were emitted at A and B . Since two light signals reach M at the same time ($AM = BM$), the observer M concludes that event- A and event- B was simultaneous.

However, the observer M would discover that the two light signals does not reach M' on the train at the same time. Since the train moves toward to B and away from A , the observer M' on the train would see that ray- B was earlier than ray- A reaching M' . Therefore, the event- A and event- B were not simultaneous on the train frame. This sample concludes that simultaneity is not invariant. It is related to observations: Observer M on frame S would discover two events were simultaneous but observer M' on frame S' would discover the two events were not simultaneous. Thus, time is relativity. The time for observer M' on the train must run differently compared to time for observer M on ground.

Analysis of inconsistency of simultaneity.

The inconsistency of simultaneity implies that observer M' on the train must experience time differently than observer M on the ground. This effect by relative motion of two frames is called time dilation. Let us analyze all possibilities to verify whether this effect is true.

- First, as shown in Fig. 6, according to the invariance of light speed, i.e. $c' = c$, observer M' would see the signal speeds of A' and B' are both equal to c , the same as observer M would see. The only difference is observer M' would state that the train appears stationary and the ground appears moving to left side. Since A' and B' were not moving, two light signals would reach M' at the same time. Thus, observer M' would also conclude that event- A' and event- B' was simultaneous ($A'M' = B'M'$). In addition, the motion of the train does not affect the speed of light watched on ground; the motion of ground does not affect the speed of light watched on the train!

- Someone may say that inconsistency of simultaneity comes from the observation of observer M . This implies that different observer has different conclusion. This is not true. Why observer M claims that the speed of signal A' differs the speed of signal B' ? The reason is that observer M used Galilean speed transformation $u' = u - v$ to transform the speed of photons A and B from frame S

to frame S' , and he got the speed of photon A in train frame was $c' = c - v$; the speed of photon B in train frame was $c' = c + v$; so he concluded photons A and B did not reach M' at the same time.

In fact, observer M used wrong equations, i.e. Eq. (12) and (13). If we use the correct equations, i.e. Eq. (3) and (4), the speed of photon A in train frame should be:

$$c' = (c - v)/(1 - vc/c^2) = c.$$

The speed of photon B in train frame should be:

$$c' = (c + v)/(1 + vc/c^2) = c.$$

Thus, we conclude that photons A and B did reach M' at the same time. In addition, if an observation contradicts with the measurement by observer M' , the observation is wrong. Please note that Einstein gave Eq.(4) by himself in paper [5].

- Someone may say that the reason of $c' = c$ is time dilation on the train frame. If no time dilation, photon A' should be at speed $c' = c - v$, and photon B' should be at speed $c' = c + v$. Due to time dilation, i.e. $t' < t$, the speed of photon A' in train is c . For traveling same distance, observer M' uses less time than observer M does, so observer M' lives longer. This means observer M' has experienced time dilation:

$$t' = (c - v)/AM, t = c/AM, \text{ thus } t' = [(c - v)/c]t, t' < t.$$

This explanation has a fatal flaw. If photon A' causes time dilation, photon B' would cause time contraction, i.e. observer M' would also experience time contraction. This means the speed of photon B is $c' = c + v$ originally. Due to time expansion, i.e. $t' > t$, the speed of photon B' in train is c , i.e. observer M' has experienced time expansion:

$$t' = (c + v)/BM, t = c/BM, \text{ thus } t' = [(c + v)/c]t, t' > t.$$

What is the real time relationship? $t' < t$ or $t' > t$? A moving clock go slower or faster? The thought experiment of time dilation comes from an imagination: Observer M imagines that observer M' also feels the train is moving, thus, observer M' would conclude $c - v$ and $c + v$.

According to the principle of relativity, there is no priority frame. For which frame is moving, observer M and M' have opposite views since motion is relative. If time-dilation occurs because the train is moving. The time-dilation would also occur on ground because the ground is moving. So, the statement of time dilation is contradictory. It is not logical.

- Events A and B are only special cases that are related to light signals. Why do two special events lead to a general rule of inconsistency of simultaneity? If events A and B are bullet shootings, the two events that occur on the train are definitely different from those that occur on the ground, since the train will cause the bullet to have an initial speed. But, the train will not cause photons to have an initial speed. That is why $c' = c$. Therefore. **The inconsistency of simultaneity does not exist.**

2.2 The space varies between frames S and S'

Fig. 7 is a similar a sample that Einstein used to explain space-interval varies between two frames of reference. A fly-man carrying a flashlight flies in space at speed $v = 0.8c$. A ground observer would measure the speed of light from the flashlight to be c since the motion of light source (the fly-man) does not affect the speed of light.

However, the ground observer would discover that the fly-man would see the speed of light less than c since the fly-man is moving. From the observation, the photon speed would be $u' = c - v = 0.2c$ in fly-man frame. This phenomenon implies that the space in fly-man frame

Fig. 7

is contracted.

Analysis of the ground observer's observation.

- First, the fly-man would see the speed of the light to be also c according to the principle of relativity. The fly-man would feel his frame is stationary, and ground frame is moving. In this case, should we trust the ground observation or should we trust the measurement in fly-man frame? Of course, the fly-man's measurement represents the correct answer.
- Why the observation from ground would discover the speed of light in fly-man frame is slower? The reason is the ground observer use a wrong equation to transform light speed c from ground frame to fly-man frame. As per Eq.(12), the result of transformation is

$$c' = c - v = 0.2c$$

If we use a correct equation, the result of transformation will be the same as the result of measurement in fly-man frame. As per Eq.(3), the result of transformation is:

$$c' = (c - 0.8c)/(1 - 0.8c^2/c^2) = c$$

No any contradiction at all!

- Someone may imagine that the speed of the light in fly-man frame is c since the space in fly-man frame is contracted. This imagination has a fatal flaw. If the flashlight points to opposite direction, the result of transformation as per Eq.(13) will be:

$$c' = c + v = 1.8c$$

Is the space in fly-man frame contracted or expanded?

2.3 Definition of simultaneity

In Einstein's Paper-4 [4], Pg.3, Einstein gave the definition of the two clocks synchronize if:

$$t_B - t_A = t'_A - t_B \tag{19}$$

$$2AB/(t'_A + t_A) = c \tag{20}$$

AB at Eq.(19) are the distance of two endpoints of a moving rigid rod. A light signal traveled from A to B at time t_A , and reached B at time t_B . And then, the light signal was reflected from B to A at time t_B , and reached back to A at time t'_A . If the "time" required for light travel from A to B is equal to the "time" required for light travel from B and A , then A time is equal to B time. Eq.(20) implies that distance AB is related to the rate change of time interval and light speed. Note: original paper shows $2AB/(t'_A - t_A) = c$.

Analysis of the Definition of simultaneity.

What does "two clocks synchronize" mean? If the rates of time interval of clock A and B are the same, clock A synchronizes with clock B . Thus, if AB -rod is at rest on stationary frame S , and it is viewed by observer S , the clock A would synchronize with clock B since observer S is also at rest on stationary frame S . A time = B time means the rates of time interval are the same. However, If AB -rod is moving, only the moment in which clock A overlaps with observer clock S (a clock rests in stationary frame S), the clock A would synchronize with clock S since AS distance = 0. When clock A synchronizes with clock S , clock A would not synchronizes with clock B because AB -rod is moving. In this case, A time \neq B time, i.e. events A and B are not simultaneous. We guess above description is the original meaning of Einstein's paper. Now, let's discuss this new definition of time in detail.

1. If AB -rod is moving, what would observer S' (observer S' is at rest on AB -rod) see? He would see that AB -rod is stationary and frame S is moving. If a light signal travels from A to B , the times

required for light travels from A to B and from B to A would be the same because the invariance of light speed is valid in frame S' . Thus, observer S' would confirm A time = B time, i.e. clock A synchronizes with clock B .

2. The problem is the observer S , who is at rest in stationary frame S , would imagine that A time $\neq B$ time by a thought experiment which is based on flowing assumption:

When light travels from point A to B , the light speed on AB -rod is $c' = c - v$ since the moving directions of the light and AB -rod are the same. When light travels from point B to A , the light speed on AB -rod is $c' = c + v$ since the moving directions of the light and AB -rod are opposite. This thought experiment implies that Galilean transformation is universally correct. Again, no matter what imagination observer S has the measuring result of the light speed on AB -rod would be always c . If observer S uses correct equations to imagine his thought experiment, he would discover there is no contraction between his view and the view of observer S' . In this case, when light travels from point A to B , the light speed on AB -rod would be:

$$\text{As per Eq.(3)} \quad c' = (c - v)/(1 - vc/c^2) = c$$

When light travels from point B to A , the light speed on AB -rod would be:

$$\text{As per Eq.(4)} \quad c' = (c + v)/(1 + cv/c^2) = c$$

Since light speed on AB -rod is always equal to c , observer S' would also conclude A' time = B' time. Whatever events A and B are viewed in frame S or S' , there is only one answer. There is no simultaneous contradiction whatsoever unless observer S did a wrong thought experiment or observer S forces the observer S' to accept his wrong thought experiment.

If all clocks including clocks on AB -rod are standard atomic clocks, it would be A time = B time = S time regardless photon motion. In addition, photons will never be stuck along AB -rod. Light signal will travel in the sky freely regardless of the relative motion between AB -rod and ground.

3. Someone may ask a question. Why GPS clocks need to be modified? Please read paper [3] to understand what MATHEMATICAL clock is and what physical clock is. Since satellite travels in three-dimensional physical space, we should use three-dimensional Logical transformation. Satellite math clock will be slower or faster than the physical clock of satellite frame (atomic clocks), depending on the moving directions between satellite and satellite signal, and also depending on satellite locations in earth frame. The Lorentz factor is only a postulate.

2.4 Relativity of length and time

In Einstein's Paper-4 [4], Pg.5, Einstein gave the definition of the relativity of length and time:

$$r_{AB} = (t_B - t_A)(c - v) \tag{21}$$

$$\text{and } r_{AB} = (t'_A - t_B)(c + v) \tag{22}$$

r_{AB} is the length of a moving rod measured in the stationary frame. v is the moving speed of the moving rod. t_A denotes the time when a light ray was emitted at A point. t_B denotes the time when the ray reached at B point. t'_A denotes the time when the ray is reflected back from B point to A point.

Please read Einstein original paper at least five times. This is the hard part to interpret the original meaning of Einstein's paper.

Analysis of the Relativity of length and time.

1. Let's interpret Eq.(21), (22) and Einstein's Paper-4 [4], Pg.4. As shown in Fig. 8, when moving

$A'B'$ -rod overlaps with stationary AB -rod, moving observers A' and B' would determine $A'B'$ -rod length according to the clock readings of A and B and coordinates of A and B in frame S . This operation is called "the length of the (moving) rod in the stationary frame". Moving observers would discover

Fig. 8

A time $\neq B$ time, since the speed of light on AB -rod is $c-v$ or $c+v$.

The length of AB -rod (r_{AB}) represents the length of $A'B'$ -rod in the stationary frame. If measure $A'B'$ -rod in frame S' , the length is r'_{AB} . Moving observer discover that $r_{AB} < r'_{AB}$, i.e. moving makes $A'B'$ -rod shorter. It is really a confusing imagination. But it is clearly disclose Einstein's thinking.

This imagination is based on an assumption, that "moving" observer also feels himself is moving and AB -rod is at rest. The postulates of time-dilation and length-contraction are the only solution to make both c and $c-v$ or $c+v$ valid. Further, Einstein believed nature time and space are combined together, called spacetime.

- Now, we are discussing Eq.(21) and (22) as per conventional wisdom. What are the clocks A and B here? Are they physical clocks? Physical clocks are atomic clocks that represent standard clock located at Greenwich, London. Since the rates of time interval of atomic clocks are all the same. Physical time is independent variable, and it is not $t=f(x, v, c)$, so clocks A and B are not physical clocks. Are they mathematical clocks? Math time is a dependent variable. It is $t^*=f(t, x, v)$, $t^* \neq t$. We agree they must be math clocks. We will further discuss this question in Section 4.2.
- " AB -rod is at rest in the system S " means AB -rod represents frame S ; " $A'B'$ -rod is at rest in the frame S' " means $A'B'$ -rod represents system S' . $S(x, y, z)$ and $S'(x', y', z')$ represent unlimited mathematical spaces. Frame S' and frame S have equal status. If we select frame S' as reference frame (i.e. we stand on frame S'), the mathematical space defined by frame S' represents physical space. In this case, frame S represents mathematical spaces, and it is moving.

The speed of photons on $A'B'$ -rod is c' ($c'=c$). If we stand on $A'B'$ -rod, we can figure out the speed of that photon on AB -rod according to Eq.(17) and (18):

$$u = (u' + v)/(1 + vu'/c^2) \quad u' \text{ direction is opposite to } v \quad (17)$$

$$u = (u' - v)/(1 - vu'/c^2) \quad u' \text{ direction is the same as } v \quad (18)$$

Where u' is a particle speed at $A'B'$ -rod, i.e. the relative speed between that photon and $A'B'$ -rod; v is the relative speed between $A'B'$ -rod and AB -rod; u is a particle speed at AB -rod, i.e. the relative speed between that photon and AB -rod. Thus,

$$c = (c' + v)/(1 + vc'/c'^2) = c'$$

$$c = (c' - v)/(1 - vc'/c'^2) = c'$$

Therefore, the conclusion is $c-v$ on Eq.(21) and $c+v$ on Eq.(22) are not correct. Relative speed between a photons and $A'B'$ -rod is c ; relative speed between a photon and AB -rod is also c ; Time dilation and space contraction do not exist.

Please note that when we transform a particle motion from frame S to frame S' , we must use math time (t^*) rather than physical time (t') to obtain the correct u' . In physics, we set $t'=t$, because all physical laws are the same between frames S and S' . If there are no particles in frames S and S' , then frames S and S' represent the relative motion of two objects, and there is no time relationship between them at all!

Again, the postulate of time dilation is based on a thought experiment which assumes Galilean transformation ($c'=c-v$, $c'=c+v$) is correct. Please read paper [3] to understand why $t^* \neq t'$.

3. Derivations of Lorentz transformation

Einstein had derived the Lorentz transformation twice using different methods. There is also a simple derivation introduced by text book [6]. All these derivations are based on a postulate of time-dilation or space contraction. All these derivations have one thing in common: using **TWO** or more photons to derive the motion relationship of **ONE** particle between frames S and S'.

S viewing S' is a term that represents an observer standing on frame S, and he observes a particle motion which is in frame S'.

3.1 Derivation of Lorentz transformation from time aspect

Please read Einstein's Paper-4 [4], Pg.5-9 first. See Fig.9. We have to rewrite the derivation since original expression are very difficult to understand. We use P₁ denotes a photon moving in the positive direction of x'-axis. P₂ denotes a photon moving in the negative direction of x'-axis. P₃, P₄ denotes photons moving in the positive directions of y'-axis and z'-axis respectively.

Fig. 9

Please note that the original symbol x' represents the location of a photon as per Einstein's Paper-4 [4], Pg.6. Since Lorentz transformation is derived from photon motions, x and x' should be photon locations in frames S and S'. For logically understanding related equations, we use symbol x instead of x' in Eq.(25), (27), (28), (29) and (30).

When the y'-axis overlapped with the y-axis, we set t = 0 and t' = t'_0 = 0. At this moment, a ray P₁ was emitted from the origin of the frame S'. When S viewing S', the speed of P₁ is c - v in frame S', so t'_1 - t'_0 = x' / (c - v), i.e. t'_1 = x' / (c - v) + t'_0. At the time t' = t'_1, the P₁ was reflected as P₂, and moved toward the origin of the frame S' with a speed c + v, and arrived to the origin of frame S' at t' = t'_2, so t'_2 - t'_1 = x' / (c + v), i.e. t'_2 = x' / (c + v) + x' / (c - v) + t'_0. According to Eq.(19), t'_2 - t'_1 = t'_1 - t'_0, we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2}(t'_0 + t'_2) = t'_1 \tag{23}$$

Inserting the value of t'_0, t'_1, t'_2 into the Eq.(23):

$$\frac{1}{2} [t'(0,0,0,t) + t' \left(0,0,0,t + \frac{x'}{c-v} + \frac{x'}{c+v}\right)] = t'(x',0,0,t + \frac{x'}{c-v}) \tag{24}$$

Einstein gave the following differential equation from Eq. (24) (No one knows how):

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{c-v} + \frac{1}{c+v} \right) \frac{\partial t'}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial t'}{\partial x'} + \frac{1}{c-v} \frac{\partial t'}{\partial t} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\partial t'}{\partial x'} + \frac{v}{c^2-v^2} \frac{\partial t'}{\partial t} = 0$$

Einstein assumed t' is a linear function, and gave an equation as follows:

$$t' = a \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2-v^2} x \right) \quad \text{where } a = \varphi(v) \tag{25}$$

Observer S' witness the speed of P₁ in frame S' along x'-axis is c, so that

$$x' = ct' \tag{26}$$

Substituting Eq. (25) into Eq.(26):

$$x' = ca \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2-v^2} x \right) \tag{27}$$

S viewing S', the speed of P₁ in frame S' along x'-axis is c - v, thus

$$\frac{x}{c-v} = t \tag{28}$$

Please note that correct Eq.(28) should be: $\frac{x'}{c-v} = t'$

Substituting equation (28) into equation (27), we get

$$x' = a \frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2} x \tag{29}$$

Observer S' witness the speed of P_3 along y' -axis direction is c in frame S' . Inserting Eq.(25):

$$y' = ct' = ca \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2 - v^2} x \right) \tag{30}$$

Please note that we cannot understand why Eq.(30) is equal to Eq.(27).

Referring to Fig. 9 and viewing from observer S , the speed of origin of frame S' is v , and P_3 traveling to y' -axis along a sloping line with a speed c . S viewing S' , the speed of P_3 in frame S' along y' -axis is $\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$. Thus:

$$\frac{y}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} = t \tag{31}$$

Please note that correct Eq.(31) should be: $\frac{y'}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} = t'$

Along y' -axis, $x = 0$. Thus, Eq.(30) is $y' = cat$. Inserting Eq.(31), we obtain:

$$y' = a \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} y \tag{32}$$

Similarly for P_4 , we get:

$$z' = a \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} z \tag{33}$$

Einstein re-wrote the Eq.(25),(29),(32),(33), and gave following equations:

$$t' = \varphi(v) \gamma_v (t - vx/c^2)$$

$$x' = \varphi(v) \gamma_v (x - vt)$$

$$y' = \varphi(v) y$$

$$z' = \varphi(v) z \quad \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

Where the $\varphi(v)$ instead of a is an unknown function of v .

By changing v to $-v$, let frame S moving in frame S' to left side, and performing S' viewing S operations, Einstein got $\varphi(v)=1$ according to the Principle of Relativity. Thus, Einstein gave the fundamental formulas of the special relativity, called the Lorentz transformation:

$$x' = \gamma_v (x - vt) \tag{34}$$

$$t' = \gamma_v (t - vx/c^2) \tag{35}$$

$$y' = y \quad z' = z \tag{36}$$

Where $\gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$

Please note that the Lorentz factor γ_v was deleted when Einstein derived his famous speed transformation, i.e. Eq. (3) $u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2)$, from Eq. (34) and (35). The Lorentz transformation without Lorentz factor γ_v is equal to one-dimensional Logical transformation, i.e. Eq. (1) and (2).

Analysis of the derivation of Lorentz transformation from time aspect.

- We cannot fully understand above derivation because it is very confusing. In Einstein's Paper-5 [5], Pg. 20-21, Einstein described that special relativity (time dilation) is to solve the conflict between equation $c' = c - v$, $c' = c + v$ and $c' = c$, i.e. the conflict between Galilean transformation and the invariance of light speed is solved by the postulate of time dilation. In other word, Einstein believed that $c' = c - v$ or $c' = c + v$ and $c' = c$ are both correct due to the phenomenon of time dilation. The Lorentz factor represents the amount of time dilation and space contraction.
- Lorentz transformation is for the relationship of one particle motion between frames S and S' , but it was derived by four photons (P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4). We cannot understand what this logic is. Why the

time relationship and distance relationship between frame S' and S are determined by photon motions? There is no relative motion between frame S' and S in y -axis direction, why is the speed of a photon in frame S' viewed from frame S is $\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$? Does y' -axis stick photon P_3 , and make it go uphill in the space of frame S ?

- If we view frame S from frame S' , the distance between two origins of frames should be $x' = -vt$. Why Eq.(34) shows the distance is $x' = -1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} vt$?

3.2 Derivation of Lorentz transformation from space aspect

Since the above derivation is not understandable, Einstein provided second derivation in Einstein's Paper-5 [5] at Appendices 01 in 1916. As shown in Fig.10, a ray of light was emitted at the origin of frame S' at the moment when the y' -axis overlaps with the y -axis. Let that moment $t'=0, t=0$. Viewing in frame S' , at the time $t' = t'$, ray- P_1 reaches the point x' , we get $x' = ct'$ as per Eq.(14). Thus, $x' - ct' = 0$ represents the point of origin S' . Viewing in frame S , at the time $t = t$, the ray- P_1 reaches the point x , we get $x = ct$. Thus, $x - ct = 0$ represents the point of origin S . The following equation represents the relationship between origin S' and origin S :

$$(x' - ct') = \lambda(x - ct) \quad \text{where } \lambda \text{ is a constant} \quad (37)$$

Referring to Fig. 10 and viewing in frame S' , at the time $t' = t'$, the ray- P_2 reaches the point $-x'$, we get $-x' = ct'$. Thus, $x' + ct' = 0$ represents the point of origin S' . Viewing in frame S , at the time $t = t$, the ray- P_2 reaches the point $-x$, we get $-x = ct$. Thus $x + ct = 0$ represents the point of origin S . The following equation also represents the relationship between origin S' and origin S :

$$(x' + ct') = \mu(x + ct) \quad \text{where } \mu \text{ is a constant} \quad (38)$$

Since light propagation is by a series of wave fronts of light, P_1 and P_2 are the same ray of the light. We use Eq.(37) and Eq.(38) to figure out the relationship of time and distance between frames S' and S .

$$(37) + (38), \text{ we get: } x' = \frac{\lambda + \mu}{2} x - \frac{\lambda - \mu}{2} ct$$

$$(38) - (37), \text{ we get: } ct' = \frac{\lambda + \mu}{2} ct - \frac{\lambda - \mu}{2} x$$

Let $a = \frac{\lambda + \mu}{2}, b = \frac{\lambda - \mu}{2}$, we get:

$$x' = ax - bct \quad (39)$$

$$ct' = act - bx \quad (40)$$

When $t = 0$, from Eq.(39), we get the distance from origin of S' to origin of S is:

$$x' = ax \quad (41)$$

Based on Eq. (41), we took a photo at the moment $t = 0$, and found the distance $x' = 1$ measured in frame S' corresponding to the distance in frame S was:

$$\Delta x = 1/a \quad (42)$$

Based on Eq. (39), when $x' = 0, x \neq 0$, and the x value is:

$$x = (bc/a)t \quad (43)$$

On the other hand, we get the distance from origin of S' to origin of S according to Fig.10:

$$x = vt \quad (44)$$

Comparing Eq.(43) and Eq.(44), we get $v = bc/a$, i.e.:

$$b = av/c \quad (45)$$

Based on Eq. (40), when $t' = 0$, we insert Eq.(45), thus:

Fig. 10

$$t = vx/c^2 \tag{46}$$

Substituting Eq.(45) and Eq.(46) into Eq.(39):

$$x' = a(1 - v^2/c^2)x \tag{47}$$

Based on Eq. (47), we took a photo at the moment $t'=0$, and found the distance $x = 1$ measured in frame S corresponding to the distance in frame S' was:

$$\Delta x' = a(1 - v^2/c^2) \tag{48}$$

According to the principle of relativity, the length contraction on both frames is equivalent, so the right sides of Eq.(42) and Eq.(48) are equal:

$$a(1 - v^2/c^2) = 1/a$$

Hence, we get

$$a = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \tag{49}$$

Substituting Eq.(49) and Eq.(45) into Eq.(39) and Eq.(40), we obtain the **Lorentz transformation**:

$$x' = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}) (x - vt) \tag{34}$$

$$t' = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}) (t - vx/c^2) \tag{35}$$

$$y' = y \quad z' = z \tag{36}$$

The Eq.(36) is obtained from Fig.10. The y and z coordinates of ray- P_3 are always the same between frame S' and S'. Referring on Fig.10, if we view in frame S', the frame S is moving to left side. Using the same method as above derivation and replacing v by -v, we get the **inverse Lorentz transformation**:

$$x = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})(x' + vt') \tag{50}$$

$$t = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})(t' + vx'/c^2) \tag{51}$$

$$y = y' \quad z = z' \tag{52}$$

Analysis of the derivation of Lorentz transformation from space aspect.

- Referring to Fig. 8 and Eq. (21), (22), length contraction is based on the postulate of time dilation ($A \text{ time} \neq B \text{ time}$). Above derivation is based on a postulate that the distance between the two origins of frames S and S' is a geometric distance plus a spatial contraction or expansion based on the motions of photons P_1 and P_2 . As shown in Fig. 11, Eq.(37) represents AB geometric distance plus a spatial contraction factor; Eq.(38) represents AC geometric distance plus a spatial expansion factor. These two opposite space changes are mutually valid for frames S', thus, the Lorentz transformation is obtained.

Fig. 11

- Eq.(37) indicates the relationship of two origins of frames S' and S when photon P_1 moving to right side while Eq.(38) indicates the relationship of two origins when another photon P_2 moving to left side. The Lorentz transformation is for one particle motion but it is derived from two particle motions. Why photons are so powerful? If Lorentz transformation is for spacetime relationship between frames S and S', rather than for particle motion, why particle P_1 and P_2 are required for the derivation? Please see Fig. 4. If we remove particle Q, we only have geometric relationship between frames S and S', i.e. $x' = f(x, t, v)$; but we don't have time relationship between frames S and S'. Physical time is an independent variable both in frames S and S'. Photon speed is defined by physical time and distance. How can be time and space determined by two photons?
- The derivation is only for the relationship of two origins, why the relationship of these two special points can represent the relationship of unlimited points? The condition of the deviation is: when P_1

and P_2 started moving, the clocks of t' and t was reset, i.e. $t' = t = 0, x' = x = 0$. When P_1 and P_2 continues to move, the initial condition is magically changed: when $t = 0, x' \neq x = 0$, i.e.

$x' = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})x$ (Eq.(41)); when $x' = 0, x \neq x' = 0$, i.e. $x = vt$ (combining Eq. (43) and (45)); when $t' = 0, t \neq t' = 0$, i.e. $t = vx/c^2$ (Eq.(46)); and so on. All this operation is called "snapshot".

Obviously, it violates causality.

- The derivation implies frame S' appears to be contracted when it is viewed from frame S ; frame S appears to be contracted when it is viewed from frame S' . Thus, Eq.(42) and Eq.(48) are equivalent. This means there is no common logic between observers S and S' . Is contracting space mathematical or physical or natural?

3.3 Derivation of time-dilation

The following is a popular derivation of time-dilation in text books. As shown in Fig.12, a moving train has a light source A' on the floor and a mirror B' under ceiling. B' and A' align vertically, and the distance is h . If a ray of light P_1 is emitted at A' , how much time required for the ray P_1 from A' to B' ?

An observer in the frame S' will gives following answer since the train is stationary:

$$\Delta t' = h/c \tag{53}$$

An observer in frame S will gives another answer. Since the train is moving, when the ray P_1 reaches to B' from A' , the train has moved vt distance. The P_1 traveling path is:

$$d = \sqrt{(v \Delta t)^2 + h^2} \tag{54}$$

Thus, the time required for the ray P_1 from A' to B' is:

$$\Delta t = d/c \tag{55}$$

Combing these Eq.(54) and (55), we obtain:

$$\Delta t = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}) h/c \tag{56}$$

Inserting Eq. (53), we get a time relationship:

$$\Delta t = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}) \Delta t' \quad \Delta t > \Delta t' \tag{57}$$

Therefore, time-dilation is described as follows:

Measuring in the moving frame S' , the time-interval of two events occur in the frame S' is $\Delta t'$.

Measuring in the stationary frame S , the time-interval of the same two events occur in the frame S' is Δt . Due to $\Delta t > \Delta t'$, it means a moving clock goes slower.

Analysis of the derivation of time-dilation.

- First of all, an observer in frame S would witness the ray P_1 went vertically from A to B in frame S as shown in Fig.13, since the train moving does not affect the travel of ray P_1 . The time required for the ray P_1 from A to B is $\Delta t = h/c$. Thus, no time-dilation between frames S and S' .
- Why observer S discovers the ray went a sloping path in frame S' and spent more time? Referring Fig.13, the photon went a sloping path is P_2 , not P_1 . It is impossible for the train draws a photon goes a sloping path. When time is $\Delta t = h/c$, P_2 was at C , not B' . Therefore, Eq.(54) and (56) are only from a illusion. The Δt in Eq.(57) does not make any sense. Therefore, we conclude that time-dilation does not exist.

Fig.12

Fig. 13

4. From Lorentz transformation to relativistic space and time

In Einstein's Paper-4 [4], Pg.9-11, Einstein explained the physical meaning of Lorentz transformation. That is "Physical Meaning of the Equations Obtained in Respect to Moving Rigid Bodies and Moving Clocks".

4.1 Physical Meaning of the Equation (34) regarding a moving rigid bodies

Einstein wrote in paper [4], Pg.10: "We envisage a rigid sphere of radius R , at rest relatively to the moving system S' , and with its centre at the origin of co-ordinates of S' . Viewing from frame S , the motion of frame S' makes the rigid sphere in "the x dimension appears shortened in the ratio 1: $\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, i.e. the greater the value of v , the greater the shortening." It becomes an ellipsoid.

Analysis of the shortening of moving rigid bodies in x direction.

1. Physics defined a ruler to measure length. Physics assumes the length of this ruler is never changed. This ruler now is defined by light travel. If space interval for light travel varies in different frames, it means the interval of NATURE space varies in different frames. No one can perceive this "varies" because we are all inside ONE nature space. If "relativity of length" means relativity of nature space, no one can prove this statement is wrong or correct but God. However, we can do a logical analysis to discover the possibility of "relativity of nature space".

2. Referring to paper [1] and [3], transformation equations are for transforming a particle motion speed (including physical quantities) from frame S to frame S' . Due to $u = dx/dt$, the x and t transformations are for deriving speed transformations, etc.

When Einstein derived equation $u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2)$ from Eq. (34) and (35), the Lorentz factor was deleted. So the equations $m = \gamma(u)m_0$ and $E = mc^2$ are obtained without Lorentz factor. The x' and x in Eq.(34) represent the location of a particle, not the length of a rigid body.

3. "A moving rod appears shorter" is only a postulate. This postulate is not logical, because it will lead to an opposite conclusion. A moving rod represents a moving frame S' , and frames S' and S are in relative motion. From point of view of frame S' , frame S is moving, i.e. "a stationary rod appears shorter". The principle of relativity requires spatial homogeneous and isotropy for each frame of reference. Any observation which violates this rule is merely an illusion.

For example, there are two banks at opposite sides. If bank B is viewed from bank A , the exchange rate would appear 1 USD = 0.7 EUR; but if bank A is viewed from bank B , the exchange rate would appear 1 EUR = 0.7 USD. Since reference frames are unlimited, the answers are relativity and unlimited, no any common answer. Thus, we can say the physical laws in the moving frame appear wrong. Therefore, the statement of "A moving rod appears shorter" is not logical self-consistent.

4. Let's figure out whether Lorentz transformation leads to a moving rod appear "the x dimension appears shortened in the ratio 1: $\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ ". The Lorentz coordinate transformation is:

$$x' = \gamma_v(x - vt) \quad \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \tag{34}$$

"Rigid sphere of radius R , at rest relatively to the moving system S' " and "at the origin of system S' " mean $x'=0$. Thus, from Eq. (34), we obtain $x = vt$, but x' is not shown; no "shorter" is found.

If we set $t=0$, we would get $x' = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}) x$. It means $x' > x$ ($\Delta x' = x'$, $\Delta x = x$, due to $x'_1 = x_1 = 0$), so the conclusion is that a rigid sphere appears longer, not shorter!

5. How can we make it shorter? It is easy. Let's use inverse Lorentz coordinate transformation, Eq.(50):

$$x = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})(x' + vt') \tag{50}$$

When $t'=0, x'=0$, we obtain $x = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}) x'$, that is $x' < x$. The rigid sphere appears shorter!

Since we can get opposite results from Eq.(34) and Eq.(50) respectively, we can choose an equation arbitrarily for what kind of answer we want. Therefore, the statement of "A moving rod appears shorter" is only an arbitrarily imagination, no logic inside.

6. If the rigid sphere is not at S' origin, the "contraction or expansion" is not only related to v but also related to t . The Eq.(34) can be written as:

$$\gamma_v x - x' = \gamma_v v t, \quad \gamma_v = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}), \quad \Delta x' = x', \quad \Delta x = x, \quad \text{due to } x'_1 = x_1 = 0.$$

The rate of "contraction or expansion" is increasing over time. In addition, we can set a frame on any moving object. If "A moving rod appears shorter" represents the of nature space, it would be out of our imagination, since the nature space pattern is too complicated!

4.2 Physical Meaning of the Equation (35) regarding a moving clock

Einstein wrote paper [4], Pg.10-11: a clock at the origin of frame S' and represents t' . "What is the rate of this clock, when viewed from the stationary system?", "Whence it follows that the time marked by the clock (viewed in the stationary system) is slow by $1 - \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ seconds per second", comparing the clock at stationary system.

"We arrive at this result: If one of two synchronous clocks at A is moved in a closed curve with constant velocity until it returns to A , the journey lasting t seconds, then by the clock which has remained at rest. The travelled clock on its arrival at A will be $tv^2/2c^2$ second slow."

Analysis of time-dilation of moving clocks.

1. Is the travel clock measuring nature time? Physics uses atomic clocks to measure physical time. The atomic clock is defined by several periods of the energy transition of the cesium 133 atom. Physics assumes these "periods" are never changed. No one can perceive these "periods" are changed because no one can compare the previous "periods" to current "periods". If we say nature time is changed, it means these "periods" are changed. Therefore, if the travelled clock represents nature time, and it went slower, no one can verify this statement is wrong or correct but God. We cannot answer where the natural clock for natural time is. We know we are in physics time of 2019, not natural time. We agree if "relativity of time" means "relativity of mathematical time". If "relativity of time" means "relativity of nature time", what we can do is to discover the possibility by a logical analysis.
2. "Time dilation" is only a postulate. This postulate is a logical inconsistent imagination, because it will lead to an opposite conclusion. Motion is relative. "A moving clock appears slow" leads to "A stationary clock appears slow".
Which clock goes slower? For example, if we set $v = 0.9 c$, the amount of slowness is $tv^2/2c^2 = 0.4t$. We assume that observers A, B, C have only 50 years of life left.
Now, observer A stays on the earth; observer B carries clock- B and takes a trip flying from left circle, and returns to point A after 60 years; observer C carries clock- C and takes a trip flying from right circle, and returns to point A after 60 years. The amount of nature time change is $0.4t = 0.4 \times 60 = 24$ years. Who is still alive? Do observers B and C would both appear alive? Is observer A in an ABSOLUTE stationary frame? Who is younger? Observer B or observer C ?
3. Let's figure out whether Lorentz transformation leads to "a moving clock appears slows by $1 - \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ seconds per second". The Lorentz time transformation is:

$$t' = \gamma_v(t - vx/c^2) \quad \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad (35)$$

"A clock at the origin of frame S'" means $t'=0$. Thus, from Eq.(35), we obtain $t = vx/c^2$, but t' is not shown; no "slow" is found.

If we set $x=0$, we would get $t' = t(1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})$, It means $t' > t$ ($\Delta t' = t'$, $\Delta t = t$, due to $t'_1 = t_1=0$), so the conclusion is that a moving clock appears faster, not slower!

How can we make "a moving clock appears slower" ? It is easy. Let's use inverse Lorentz time transformation, Eq.(51):

$$t = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})(t' + vx'/c^2) \quad (51)$$

When $x'=0$, we obtain $t = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}) t'$, that is $t' < t$. The moving clock appears slower!

Since we can get opposite results from Eq.(35) and Eq.(51) respectively, we can choose an equation arbitrarily for what kind of the answer we want. Therefore, the statement of "A moving clock appears slower" is only an arbitrarily imagination, no logic inside.

4. If the moving clock is not at S' origin, the "time dilation or contraction" is not only related to v but also related to x . The Eq.(35) can be written as:

$$\gamma_v t - t' = \gamma_v vx/c^2, \quad \gamma_v = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}). \quad \Delta t' = t', \quad \Delta t = t, \quad \text{due to } t'_1 = t_1=0.$$

The rate of "time dilation or contraction" is increasing as x increase. If the moving clock represents nature time, it would be out of our imagination, since the time pattern is too complicated!

5. Conclusion

Special relativity is only a hypothesis. In order to eliminate the conflict between Galilean transformation ($c' = c - v$) and the principle of relativity ($c' = c$), Einstein proposed the special relativity, which changes current physical definitions of time and distance. Einstein used Galilean transformation ($c' = c - v$ or $c' = c + v$) to derive special relativity, i.e. Lorentz transformation, and then Galilean transformation is replaced by Lorentz transformation. Einstein also used the hypothesis of the relativity of length and time to derive Lorentz transformation, and then time dilation and length contraction are given by the Lorentz factor.

The concept of relativity of time is from the observation of inconsistency of simultaneity, but this observation is based on Galilean transformation. The concept of length contraction is from time dilation. However, time dilation and length contraction are not measuring values in a moving frame; they are the results of observations from an observer in stationary frame. Einstein assumed the conflict between the measurements and observations can coexist. Einstein applied Lorentz transformation in two different ways. Einstein used it for transforming a particle motion from a stationary frame to a moving frame, and it leads to his famous equations $u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2)$, $m = \gamma(u)m_0$, $E = mc^2$ by deleting Lorentz factor; Einstein also used the Lorentz factor to hypothesize time dilation and length contraction, which are regardless of particle motion.

Whatever using which way to explain the derivations and interpretations of Lorentz transformation, it does not satisfy logical self-consistent and causal logic; no one is able to understand the exact meaning and the exact mathematical logic.

In fact, if we understand the physical concept of relative motion of two reference frames, we should be able to understand why $c' = c$, and what math time is. We should use a correct transformation, which is logical transformation, to replace Galilean transformation and Lorentz transformation; use logical transformation to make observations and to obtain equations for high-energy physics and quantum mechanics.

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